

EFFORTS TO IMPROVE AND IMPROVE THE QUALITY OF LECTURES ON BASIC MATHEMATICS COURSE I THROUGH SOLVING PROBLEMS SYSTEMATICALLY (PSSS)

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Abstract

Efforts to improve and develop the quality of lectures for students in various disciplines need to get serious attention. Because lately it seems that the curriculum that applied to education world tend to be theoretical. In order for the content between theoretical and practical, to be balanced, then the lecturer should be more creative and innovative to find methods that match the character of the course with the students. In order to study basic mathematics course I give better problem solving ability than teaching by using method of Kulponasi and systematic problem solving technique (PSSS) is one alternative solution. Learning by using the method of Kulponasi and PSSS techniques one of them aim to improve students' ability in solving basic mathematics problems I is expected to provide convenience for students to get a better method of learning. The results achieved in this study show that the student participation rate is very high. This increase is also followed by a numerical increase in the value of learning results.

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1. Introduction

What is meant by the development of lectures is an effort to improve the quality of the lectures. The lectures are said to be of good quality if; 1) the content corresponds to the purpose of the lecture, and is not outdated, 2) students mastered well the material and reasoning process in the field of the studied science. So they are able to develop their skills and knowledge independently.

Novak in Syaiful [1996] for mathematics, the mastery of a good lecture is; 1) understand the concepts, techniques and methods in the lecture well, true (no misconception) and steady, which can be identified, among others, in the form of the ability to explain the notion of concepts with simple language, explaining interpretations in everyday life or in other fields of science and skillfully apply techniques and methods correctly and appropriately, 2) have a comprehensive picture of the contents of the lecture, and able to show or explain the relationship between the concepts in the course and the relevance to other courses in the environment or outside the field of science.

In order to realize the good lectures, the lecturer needs to; 1) mastering the course well in the sense as expressed above, 2) presenting the lecture well, so that it appeals to the students (motivated students and the information provided is easily digested according to students' ability and background).

Further, Novak [1985] says teaching is an activity to get a person or a group of people to master something or some ability. What is meant by the ability in this discussion is the ability in one area of science. In this case the field of mathematics. Because of the extent of knowledge, this process is done part by part and gradually or more clearly in the form of a series of lectures in a sequence that corresponds to the level of difficulty and logical order of the structure of science.

A good way of teaching relies heavily on the form of discipline that is taught, a good way of teaching for each subject or field of science is continuously developed and perfected, because science is always evolving and its development is very rapid.

Traditionally the students or students were taught all the information known by the lecturer, but lately they were taught to learn and supplemented with fundamental and strategic information, so that they were able to utilize the information they obtained to complement, develop and improve their own knowledge in accordance with needs and wants. Teachers act more or less as motivators, directors and resource persons, this is necessary because science is advancing and expanding very rapidly.

Therefore, it is important that the limited lecture time be chosen on the topic / subject that will be given correctly, and in the lecture the students are trained to be able to develop the topic discussed by self-study, for example starting with regular and monitored reading tasks. Therefore the chosen topic must be fundamental and strategic. It should not be forgotten to detect and add concepts that are preconditions that students may not have mastered for each course. This step can only be done if the course to be taught is well controlled by the lecturer. All this requires good preparation.

To do this selection of the concept, first write down the points and concepts put forward in the reference book used. From here derive the fundamental and strategic concepts mentioned above, which can be taught in the very limited time available for the lecture. Taking into account the prerequisite concepts required for this lecture and checking for any prerequisite concepts that students have not yet acquired, this concept should be included as a concept to be taught in this lecture. Seeing all the concepts that need to be taught in the time available, taking into account the ability and background of students, it is necessary to determine how the college approach that will be pursued.

All of this is included and described in what we would call a college outline. The outline of this lecture is an essay that tells about the lecture, which includes among others; 1) strategic concepts to be taught, 2) mastery of matter, 3) skills and skills expected of students, 4) approach the lecture, 5) the role of lecturers and student roles, 6) an evaluation process to be performed, and 7) exercises to be given and so on.

By reading the outline of this lecture, people will be able to see the breadth and depth of the lecture, the ability of students who have attended this lecture, and how about the implementation. Basic Mathematics courses (I and II) are compulsory subjects in Mathematics and Natural Sciences (PMIPA) Department of Jambi University. Of these subjects (especially basic math I) students are expected to understand well the topics about the rate of derivation and the application of the derivatives. Besides, students are also able to understand well about Integration.

Based on the above, the author is interested to conduct, a class action research (CAR) to improve the effectiveness of different lectures with the usual lectures. The author designed the method of Solving

Problems Systematically (PSSS) in such a way that allows students to understand the existing concepts and can solve the problem well.

1.1 Research Problems

The problem of this research is the low activity of students and the ability of the students of Mathematics Education Study Program of Faculty of Teacher Training and Education of Jambi University in basic mathematics lecture I. Problems encountered include; 1) lack of student activity in basic mathematics lecture me, 2) the lack of student mastery in basic mathematical concepts I, 3) it is impossible for students to solve basic math problems I systematically. Based on the background can be formulated research problems as follows; 1) is the use of Kulspensi and PSSS Techniques, suitable for use in lecture calculus I?, and 2) how to implement a CMS and PSSS techniques effectively, in order to improve student learning in basic mathematics I.

1.2 Research Purposes

Implementation of this research with the aim to; 1) find out if the PSSS response and techniques are suitable for basic I. lectures, 2) recognizing the effective way in implementing KulSSsi and PSSS techniques that can improve the quality of the basic mathematics lecture I, and 3) making sure whether the PSSS technique can complement the previously given action (kulponasi), to improve the quality of the basic math lecture I.

1.3 Research Methods

The type of research used is classroom action research, with the subject of research is the students of the Mathematics Education Program, Faculty of Teacher Training and Education Jambi University who follow the lectures of basic mathematics I academic year 2016/2017

1.4 The Proposed Solution

Prior to the study, the steps taken were; a) assessing the basic mathematics course synopsis I, and b) create teaching materials on the problem and solving using PSSS technique

In accordance with the hypothesis, which is designed for the purposes of this study are as follows:

- a. Providing information on PSSS techniques, and some examples of solutions problem with PSSS technique.
- b. Selects textbooks in Indonesian that match the topics within basic mathematics I
- c. Prepare questions for each subject for homework assignments.

2. Expected Results

With applied actions, it is expected:

- a. At the time of primary mathematics lecture me, students appear to be active and not just a spectator.
- b. Students can solve basic math problems I in a way systematic.

- c. The value of the first low grade mathematics learning result will be high.
- d. There is an increased understanding of the concept of Calculus I students.
- e. In every basic mathematics task I have given lectures, the students as soon as possible to complete the concerned.

3. Implementation Research activities in every meeting hour in general are as follows:

- a. At the beginning the lecture explains the textbook to be used and gives an explanation of how to systematically solve problems (PSSS) and some examples of problem solving (distributed to students).
- b. The lecturer gives an explanation of the theory of concepts and gives examples of representative yang. The presentation of the material is aided by a whiteboard or projector, overhead and completes the given lecturer (material summary). The discussion of sample, examples uses a consistent, explicit and systematic problem solving tips. In this case systematic problem solving (PSSS) is used.
- c. To the students are given exercises to be done at home must be collected. At the time of reponsi will be discussed with students, then assessed and returned. Students are also given training that must be done independently or guided training.

4. Data collection

The data collection in the activities is done by the lecturer, continuously every cycle of action implementation. Using instruments: diaries, questionnaires, interview guides, tests. Sources of information are students, student activities and learning atmosphere. There are two types of data required from the students, namely: activity through lecture during presentation of basic mathematics material I. Besides, students' participation in problem solving and guided exercises using PSSS techniques are; student learning activities through Kulponsi in the classroom viewed by way of direct observation by researchers who are following the lecture. The effectiveness of guided exercises and the use of PSSS techniques can be assessed based on what the student wrote (checking student self-study) or from mistakes made.

4.1 Monitoring

Monitoring is done with the instrument that has been done. This monitoring will be continuous by the lecturer on every action implementation activity.

4.2 Data Analysis

The collected data is analyzed by the lecturer. In terms of analysis of this data will be done spontaneously and planned. Spontaneous data analysis is performed immediately after the implementation of the action in question. Data analysis was done by deductive and inductive thinking analysis technique. Analysis of

deductive and inductive thinking will be imposed on data obtained from questionnaires, interviews and observations. The results of data analysis will be checked and diricek. This is intended to obtain relatively accurate analysis results for follow-up decision making. The conclusion is drawn by the lecturer. The conclusion will be drawn by the inductive thinking, ie by comparing the results of the analysis and the success criteria (the expected result at point 4). In conducting the study with Kulponi and PSSS techniques on basic mathematics I will find things that make students less active in the learning process. This may be due to unfamiliarity with PSSS techniques, knowledge of the prerequisites. The things found will be useful and used to design and implement actions in the next cycle. From the data of learning result, observation, interview and questionnaire in one cycle can be used to know whether the lecture with Kulponi and PSSS technique can increase student activity to basic mathematics I. This data is useful to know whether PSSS technique can improve the ability of solving basic mathematics problem I.

5.Results and Discussion

1. Learning Process

The learning of the basic mathematics course I using PSSS technique is given every example giving and solving the problems as an exercise. In solving the problem, students quickly adjusted to the applied pattern, following the PSSS procedure as applied in chapter II. In the observation of every lesson, the fundamental thing that becomes an obstacle for students is to translate the matter into the appropriate mathematical model. If this is resolved then the PSSS method is easily applied. The use of PSSS technique is actually making students more motivated in the lecture. This can be seen from the given questionnaire. The full results can be seen in table 1 below:

Table 1. Observation Results About Learning Models

No	Item Number	Opinion							
		Strongly agree		Agree		Disagree		Strongly Disagree	
		Total	%	Total	%	Total	%	Total	%
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)
1	1	224	10,81	33	89,19	0	0,00	3590	0,00
2	2	6	16,22	30	81,08	1	2,70	0	0,00
3	3	8	21,62	28	75,68	1	2,70	0	0,00
4	4	8	21,62	23	62,16	6	16,22	0	0,00
5	5	11	10,81	22	59,46	4	10,81	0	0,00
6	6	10	29,73	21	56,76	6	16,22	0	0,00
7	7	8	27,03	23	62,16	6	16,22	0	0,00
8	8	10	27,02	25	67,57	2	5,41	0	0,00
9	9	13	35,14	23	62,16	1	2,70	0	0,00
10	10	18	48,65	17	45,95	2	2,70	0	0,00
11	11	9	23,32	25	67,57	3	8,11	0	0,00
12	12	17	45,95	19	51,35	1	2,70	0	0,00
13	13	16	43,24	18	48,65	2	5,41	0	0,00

14	14	8	21,62	21	56,76	6	16,22	0	5,41
15	15	10	27,03	26	70,27	1	2,70	0	0,00
16	16	5	13,51	26	70,27	6	16,22	0	0,00
17	17	14	37,84	22	59,46	1	2,70	0	0,00
18	18	7	18,92	27	72,97	3	8,11	0	0,00
19	19	9	24,32	27	72,97	1	2,70	0	0,00
20	20	10	27,03	23	62,16	4	10,81	0	0,00

From table 1 above shows that the students are very fond of the applied teaching model. Proven that 64.73% agreed and 27.16% stated strongly agree and only 7.70% stated not agree even only 0.41% stated strongly disagree.

5.1 Value of Learning Outcomes

As a learning process, the value of learning results one of the indicators to see whether the learning process is successful. By using KulSSsi and PSSS Technique method, student's learning achievement score can be recorded in table 2 below.

Table 2. The Value of Student Learning Result in Basic Mathematics I Subject

No	Letter Value	amount	Percentage
1	A	9	24.33
2	B+	5	13.51
3	B	4	10.81
4	C+	5	13.51
5	C	8	21.62
6	D+	1	2.70
7	D	1	2.70
8	E	2	5.41
9	BL	2	5.41

From the table above can also be read that there are 83.78% or 31 students get the value of C upwards and only 16.22% or 6 students who or 3 students who can be categorized get the value of fail or repeat for the same subject in the next year

3. Discussion

From the tables of research results that have been displayed in atas, can be seen that the learning process by using the method of Kulponsi and PSSS Technique is very meaningful in generating student motivation to follow the lecture process. The high interest to follow the lectures with the method of kulponsi and PSSS technique is illustrated from the opinion of the students who stated that 64.73% agreed, 27.16% stated strongly agree and only slightly stated that did not agree that only amounted to

7.70%. The high participation of students in Basic Mathematics lecture I makes the lectures become more lively and vibrant. Students tend to take the initiative to formulate their own problems that will be done so that the process of trying to always be done although not always done as expected.

The high level of student participation is also supported by the value of learning outcomes in the eyes of basic mathematics I, which obtained a very high percentage of graduation rate, that is 83.78% got C value upwards and only 2.70% started D +, even only 8, 11% of which the category did not pass. This success is possible the lecturing process is conducive enough so that the learning atmosphere feels more motivating to learn more hard. Increased motivation in this learning also possible methods used. The use of PSSS in lectures encourages students to be more active in learning and working. This is in accordance with the principle of learning mathematics is working mathematics.

4. Conclusions and Suggestions

Conclusion

From result of research can be concluded that; 1) the method of Kulponi and PSSS technique was good enough to be used in the learning of basic mathematics course I, and nominally give the value of learning result which is good enough, and 2) techniques PSSS can increase motivation and participation of students in learning mathematics courses basic I.

Suggestion

From the research results and the figures obtained can be suggested; 1) each lecture in order to be carried out systematic workmanship, 2) lecturers get used to giving practice questions using PSSS technique, 3) students are accustomed to complete the tasks with PSSS technique in every task or lecture that followed, and 4) it is necessary to conduct more thorough research on the method of kulponi and this PSSS technique in different courses, in order to get better results.

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